

Influence of substituent position and pH on organophosphates hydrolysis catalyzed by various nanocrystalline ceria

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ABSTRACT

The dephosphorylation of naphthyl phosphate isomers was investigated on five different nanocrystalline ceria samples and at different pH to determine how physicochemical properties and reaction conditions affect catalytic performance. The reaction rate was consistently higher under acidic conditions for all samples, which was likely due to variations in the reaction mechanisms and the specific properties of ceria prepared by different methods. We also studied the adsorption of primary degradation products (naphthol isomers) and observed different adsorption capacities for individual samples, which may influence the overall reaction kinetics. In addition, FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of reaction residues on the ceria surface, which may also affect the reaction rate. The synthesis method influences the physicochemical properties of ceria, such as surface characteristics, stability, and catalytic activity. However, the position of the substituent on the organic backbone also significantly affected the decomposition of the selected organophosphorus compounds. The 2-naphthyl phosphate isomer (with the substituent in position 2) decomposed more rapidly on all samples, due to reduced steric hindrance from the organic backbone.

1. Introduction

The hydrolysis of phosphoester bonds is an important process in organic chemistry and is essential for the breakdown and formation of various biomolecules. Therefore, it is also of great interest to researchers, given their importance to many biological and chemical reactions [1–3]. A key factor influencing hydrolytic reactions is the location of the substituents on the organic molecule involved. The effect of substituent position on the phosphoester and other bond hydrolysis has been investigated in several works [4–6] as it is important for a design and optimization of chemical processes in production of pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, or in materials science [7–9]. Concretely, naphthyl phosphate isomers have been studied previously [4,5,10,11] to evaluate the differences in phosphatase enzyme activity. It has been observed that the different reactivity is related to the structural variability and accessibility of the phosphoryl group at the enzyme active site [4]. For example, phosphoryl group of 2-naphthyl phosphate (2-NPPH) can be more accessible to an active site of enzymes [11,12].

However, similar information for ceria and other nanocrystalline oxides/hydroxides showing pseudo-enzymatic activity is scarce. Li et al. [13] reported that the iron (hydr)oxide facets can change the reactivity of naturally occurring metal-based nanoparticles in phosphate hydrolysis. Furthermore, the length of the phosphate chain is also important factor [14], and many authors attribute the differences in the catalytic cleavage of the phosphoester bond to various pKa values of the leaving group [10,15]. 1/2-NPPH constitutional isomers are widely used as steric probes for determining the activity of various phosphatases [11] or to distinguish acidic and alkaline phosphatases in human serum [12, 16]. Among other uses, 1/2-NPPH isomers have been used to identify and quantify isoenzymes of alkaline phosphatase [17].

In this study, we investigated the complex relationship between the position of the substituent and hydrolysis of organic molecules containing P–O–aryl bonds (1/2-NPPH) under various pH using different ceria samples. A set of ceria samples prepared by various procedures was analyzed by a broad range of characterization techniques including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-

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transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), acid-base titration, zeta potential and particle size distribution measurements, and nitrogen physisorption to evaluate the physicochemical properties that are relevant to phosphate esters hydrolysis. The ability of ceria to cleave phosphoester bonds in biologically active molecules [18], pesticides [19], or chemical warfare agents [20] is well-known and has been reported in several studies [21,22]. Also, metal oxides, hydroxides and other materials exhibit the ability to cleave phosphoester bonds in various molecules, such as iron hydroxide [13], lanthanum hydroxide [23], copper bipyridyl [24], and others [14,25,26]. The ability of ceria-based materials to cleave phosphoester bonds is closely connected to the surface hydroxyl groups and other surface characteristics.

However, the position of the substituent on the organic backbone, which significantly affects the decomposition of selected organophosphorus compounds has not yet been systematically investigated. By investigating two structurally similar compounds with substituents in different positions (1/2-NPPH), we aim to elucidate the underlying factors governing their hydrolysis on the surface of ceria samples with distinct properties and under various reaction conditions.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals

All chemicals used for synthesis of nanomaterials were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Germany) and used without purification. 1-naphthyl phosphate monosodium (1-NPPH), 2-naphthyl phosphate monosodium (2-NPPH), 1-naphthol (1-NP), and 2-naphthol (2-NP) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Germany). Acetic acid and sodium acetate were purchased from Penta Ltd. (Czech Republic). Trizma base and Trizma HCl were also supplied by Sigma Aldrich (Germany). All chemicals were of analytical grade purity. Deionized water from a GORO Pharpur system (Goro, Czech Republic) was used in all experiments, and mixed-bed ion exchange was used for water purification.

2.2. Preparation of nanocrystalline cerium oxides

The five different nanoceria samples were prepared by wet chemical methods from cerium (III) nitrate hexahydrate as the starting precursor, and water as the only solvent. The synthesis procedures were described in detail elsewhere [27]. The ceria samples were denoted according to the preparation procedure as: Ce-AMN (precipitation with ammonium hydroxide), Ce-CARB (precipitation and annealing of cerium carbonate), Ce-HMT (homogeneous precipitation with hexamethylenetetramine), Ce-PER (refluxing of cerium peroxo-complexes), and Ce-UREA (homogeneous precipitation with urea and annealing). Using the proposed protocol (procedure), we can synthesize the powder/cerium oxide with well-defined physico-chemical properties. Under conditions of repeatability, the main parameters/characteristics, such as surface area, morphology, or crystallite size, exhibit low variability of the main parameters, which does not exceed 10 % (see [20,27,28]).

2.3. Evaluation of surface hydroxyl groups and pH(PZC)

The number of surface hydroxyl groups and pH(PZC) was determined by procedure described previously [29]. The titration was performed on an automatic titrator controlled by a PC (794 Basic Titrino, Metrohm, Switzerland). Briefly, 0.5 g of the ceria sample was suspended in solution containing 50 mL of NaCl (0.1 M), and 3 mL of HCl (0.1 M in 0.1 M NaCl) and mixed with a magnetic stirrer and bubbled with nitrogen for 30 minutes. Subsequently, the suspension was titrated with standardized NaOH solution (0.1 M in 0.1 M NaCl) until the pH = 10.5 was reached. The rate of titrant was 0.1 mL/min in 0.05 mL aliquots.

2.4. Characterization of samples

The FTIR spectra were obtained on a VERTEX 70 v IR spectrometer (Bruker, Germany) in diffuse reflectance mode (DRIFT) in the wavenumber range 4000–400 cm^{-1} at 64 scans per spectrum at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Raw FTIR data were processed in OPUS software (v. 8.7). The data were further processed in OriginPro 8.5, Microsoft Excel 2013, and Plot2.

The specific surface area and pore volume of samples were determined using nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms. Samples were degassed at 50 °C for 24 hours. Afterwards, 60-points adsorption and desorption isotherms were recorded with nitrogen (99.999 %, Linde) at liquid nitrogen temperature using an Anton Paar Instrument NOVA 3200e. All samples were measured three times with an experimental error of 5 %. Five-point Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) analysis and micropore analyses were applied to obtain total surface area and the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) model was used to determine pore volume from the nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherm.

Phase analysis was performed using a Panalytical X'PERT diffractometer in the symmetrical reflection mode (Cu $K\alpha$ = 1.5418 Å radiation, 40 kV, 30 mA) with a 1-dimensional X' Celerator detector. The morphology of powder samples drop-casted from water suspension on a silicon substrate was investigated by the FEI Nova NanoSEM 450 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) in a high-vacuum mode at 5 kV accelerating voltage.

2.5. Zeta potential and particle size distribution determinations

The zeta potential and particle size distribution of the prepared ceria samples were determined using a Lizesizer™ 500 instrument (Anton Paar, Austria). For zeta potential determination, electrophoretic light scattering (ELS) was employed, and the instrument was coupled with a Metrohm automatic titrator equipped with an 867 pH module and an 846 dosing interface, all controlled by Kalliope™ software. Samples were dispersed in deionized water and two portions of the same sample were used for each measurement. One was titrated from its natural pH to pH 12 with 0.1 M NaOH, and the other to pH 2 with 0.1 M HCl, both in 0.2 pH unit steps. The data from both titrations were combined and presented in a single graph. The zeta potential was calculated using the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski approximation method, allowing us to gain a deeper understanding of the surface chemistry and surface charge properties of the ceria samples. This information is important for assessing the stability, reactivity, and interactions of ceria materials. The hydrodynamic particle size and size distribution of the ceria nanoparticle colloids were evaluated by dynamic light scattering (DLS) using the same instrument. The instrument was equipped with a 40-mW semiconductor red laser source with a wavelength of 658 nm and it autonomously selected the optimal detection angle (15°, 90°, and 175°). The experiments were carried out under controlled conditions at a constant temperature of 25 °C. This dual-pronged approach on the Litesizer™ 500 yields comprehensive insights into both the surface charge and particle size characteristics of the ceria samples, providing an overall understanding of their behavior across various applications.

2.6. Decomposition of organophosphorus compounds

The effect of substituent position on the dephosphorylation of 1/2-NPPH in an aqueous environment was studied at different pH (without pH adjustment, pH = 4.5 and 8.2) along with the simultaneous release of a phosphate group and the formation of 1/2-NP. 50 mg of ceria sample was weighed into the 4 mL glass vial, together with 1.6 mL of H₂O or buffer (0.05 M TRIS or acetic), and 0.4 mL 1/2-NPPH (10 mM). In selected time (5, 10, 25, 45, 60, 90, and 120 min), an aliquot (50 μL) was taken and transferred into an Eppendorf vial (1.5 mL) containing 1 mL of methanol/water (60/40) solution. The Eppendorf vials were centrifuged for 5 min at 5000 RPM. Similarly, the

Fig. 1. XRD patterns (A), pore size distribution and N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms (inset plot) of prepared ceria samples (B).

Table 1

The sample specific surface area (SSA) and total pore volume obtained from nitrogen adsorption/desorption using BET and BJH analysis. Mean crystallite size calculated from XRD data.

Sample	SSA (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	CeO ₂ average crystallite size (nm) ^a
Ce-CARB	72.7 ± 0.2	0.050 ± 0.001	13.5
Ce-AMN	132.3 ± 1.9	0.132 ± 0.001	4.3
Ce-HMT	10.8 ± 1.2	0.016 ± 0.002	8.4
Ce-UREA	57.8 ± 1.2	0.044 ± 0.013	11.7
Ce-PER	191.0 ± 0.7	0.128 ± 0.001	3.5

^a The average deviation is ± 2.5 nm.

standards for 1/2-NPPH and 1/2-NP without the sorbents were prepared in the glass vials. The initial concentration of 1/2-NPPH and 1/2-NP at the reaction start was 2 mM.

The LaChrom HPLC system (Merck Hitachi) consisting of a L-7100 pump, L-7400 variable wavelength UV/VIS detector operating at 275 nm, and a Rheodyne 7725i injection valve with a 20 μL sampling loop was used. To evaluate the concentration of residual 1/2-NPPH and its main degradation product, 1/2-naphthol (1/2-NP). The HPLC analysis was performed in isocratic elution mode with methanol/water (60/40) as mobile phase (1.0 mL/min, water contained 0.1 % HCOOH) and the Arion® Polar C18 column 5 μm (100 × 4.6 mm) was used.

2.7. pH change during organophosphate decomposition

50 mg of the ceria sample was weighed into the glass vial (4 mL) and mixed with 1.6 mL of H₂O or buffer (0.05 M TRIS or acetic) and 0.4 mL 1/2-NPPH (10 mM). When the 1/2-NPPH was added, the pH was measured by the automatic titrator controlled by a PC (794 Basic Titrimo, Metrohm, Switzerland). The measurement lasted 120 min with a measurement interval of 1 minute and with constant mixing of the solution.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sample characterization

All prepared ceria samples showed type IV nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherm typical for porous and mesoporous materials with relatively small particle size (Fig. 1B) along with hysteresis of type H4 and H2 according to IUPAC classification [30]. The data are consistent

Fig. 2. DRIFTS spectra of prepared ceria samples.

with those obtained previously [27]. It is evident that the calcination/drying temperature and synthesis procedure significantly affect specific surface area (Table 1). Powder X-ray diffraction patterns (Fig. 1A) of all samples show diffraction lines characteristic for face-centered fluorite-type structure of ceria, namely (111), (200), (220), (311), (222), (400), (331) and (420) located at 28.761°, 33.281°, 47.748°, 56.561°, 59.157°, 69.594°, 76.729°, 79.108° (ICDD PDF 34-0394). The average crystallite size ranging between 4 and 14 nm was calculated from the diffraction line broadening using the Scherrer equation method. The intensity and sharpness of the diffraction line was significantly reduced for the Ce-HMT, Ce-AMN and Ce-PER samples as a result of small crystallites well below 10 nm.

The XPS confirmed variation in the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ ratio which is in accordance with our previous work [27] using the same set of ceria samples. The concentration of surface Ce³⁺ ions for all samples (shown in Table S1) was between 7 % and 16 %, the additional information can be found in [27]. The Ce-PER (16 %), Ce-HMT (11 %), and Ce-UREA (12 %) samples exhibit slightly higher concentration of Ce³⁺ species on the surface, which was related to the synthesis used.

Different particle morphology among the samples was studied by SEM (Fig. S1). As can be seen, the Ce-PER and Ce-AMN samples are formed by secondary irregular aggregates with a random distribution of size and shape, consisting of very small primary nanoparticles (as confirmed by XRD). Ce-CARB shows plate-like aggregates formed by hexagonal-shaped particles. Ce-HMT shows spherical-like uniformly distributed particles converging in bigger agglomerates, whereas Ce-UREA exhibits flake-like particles without uniform shape.

Table 2

The number of surface hydroxyl groups calculated from the titration curve and pH(PZC).

Sample	$q_{\text{OH}} \pm \text{SE}$ (mmol/g)	pH(PZC)
Ce-CARB	0.189 ± 0.005	4.6
Ce-AMN	0.113 ± 0.004	5.0
Ce-HMT	0.396 ± 0.001	8.1
Ce-UREA	0.201 ± 0.002	4.6
Ce-PER	0.140 ± 0.001	4.5

3.2. FTIR analysis

Fig. 2 shows the DRIFT spectra of prepared ceria samples. The bands observed between 3700 and 2700 cm^{-1} in all spectra represent the stretching vibration of $-\text{OH}$ groups from physically adsorbed H_2O or surface $-\text{OH}$ groups. Additionally, the band at 1635 cm^{-1} is linked to the bending frequency of molecular H_2O ($\text{H}-\text{O}-\text{H}$). The bands at 1333 and 1525 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of bicarbonate-like species ($\text{O}-\text{C}-\text{O}$). The carbonate-type species originate from the interaction between atmospheric CO_2 and cerium cations on the ceria surface. The bands found in the lower frequency range ($850-650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are attributed to the stretching vibrations of $\text{Ce}-\text{O}$ bonds [31,32]. The weak bands located at 2929 and 2852 cm^{-1} in the Ce-HMT spectrum correspond to the CH_2 stretching vibrations from the HMT residues [32].

3.3. PZC and surface hydroxyl groups

The point of zero charge has been evaluated from curves corresponding to the total concentration of protons consumed in the titration process (TOH) obtained by the transformation of measured titration curves; further details can be found elsewhere [29]. The number of surface hydroxyl groups per solid sample weight was calculated from the two equivalence points on the titration curve [29]. Fig. S2 presents the titration curves of prepared ceria samples, and the number of surface hydroxyl groups and pH of PZC are listed in Table 2. Two equivalence points are presented on the titration curves: EP1 and EP2. The EP1 represents the NaOH consumed in the neutralization of protonated surface hydroxyl groups. The increasing pH of the solution (at EP2) is connected with an excess of NaOH added to the solution when all hydroxyl groups are deprotonated. Significant variations were noted in the number of surface groups, while only the Ce-HMT sample had a significantly different PZC among the samples. The results indicate that Ce-AMN, Ce-CARB, Ce-PER, and Ce-UREA samples share similar pH

Table 3

pH of isoelectric point for the prepared composites and average particle size and polydispersity index calculated from DLS.

Sample	pH(IEP)	Average particle size from DLS (nm) \pm SE	PDI \pm SE
Ce-CARB	6.1	1773 ± 45	0.28 ± 0.02
Ce-AMN	4.8	1312 ± 52	0.19 ± 0.03
Ce-HMT	8.0	1075 ± 52	0.24 ± 0.02
Ce-UREA	6.9	2054 ± 101	0.27 ± 0.01
Ce-PER	9.6	782 ± 34	0.27 ± 0.02

(PZC) values, exhibiting a positively charged surface until pH of 5.

In contrast, the Ce-HMT sample demonstrates a notably shifted pH (PZC) in the alkaline region and the highest number of surface hydroxyl groups, resulting in a positively charged surface up to $\text{pH} = 8.07$. These findings show a strong influence of the synthesis method on the degree of hydroxylation of the ceria surface. The increased presence of surface hydroxyl groups in the Ce-HMT sample may be attributed to structural imperfections and unsaturated O^{2-} ions in the crystal lattice. Moreover, the pH(PZC) data for Ce-AMN, Ce-CARB, Ce-PER, and Ce-UREA are consistent with previous studies [18,33] showing similar values that ascend in the sequence: $\text{Ce-PER} < \text{Ce-CARB} = \text{Ce-UREA} < \text{Ce-AMN} < \text{Ce-HMT}$.

The TOH curves (Fig. S2) are connected with the release or consumed protons in the titration process depending on the pH solution, they express binding isotherms of protons. Positive TOH values represent proton association, whereas the negative TOH values correspond to the proton releasing due to the dissociation of surface acidic sites. The surface is positively charged if $\text{pH} < \text{pH}(\text{PZC})$. On the contrary, it is negatively charged if $\text{pH} > \text{pH}(\text{PZC})$. The variation in pH (PZC) value may be attributed to the ceria synthesis procedure and different types of surface hydroxyl groups because the resulting (pH)PZC value is not caused by only one type of hydroxyl group but via a combination of all types [34,35].

3.4. Particle size distribution and DLS measurements

The stability and the surface charge of ceria samples in solution was measured by zeta potential measurements. From the plot (Fig. 3A), the isoelectric point (IEP) can be obtained (Table 3). The IEP values are quite consistent with the reported values for ceria samples prepared by the different methods [36–38]. The variation of zeta potential and IEP can be related to the variation in the crystalline structure [38] and the preparation method. Nevertheless, the degree of surface hydration is

Fig. 3. Zeta potential (A) and DLS particle size distribution (B) measurements for individual ceria samples.

Fig. 4. The dependence of pH change at the time during the 1/2-NPPH decomposition on ceria samples, without pH adjustment (A) and approximate buffer capacity for the individual nanoceria samples (B).

connected to the surface -OH groups, which can be positively or negatively charged depending on the pH [38]. The measured data show that the particles are positively charged at pH levels below 4.8 due to the protonation of hydroxyl surface groups. The order of the samples is as follows: Ce-AMN, Ce-CARB, Ce-UREA, Ce-HMT, and Ce-PER. While above this value, the particles are negatively charged due to their deprotonation. The protonation/deprotonation process can be expressed by the following equations (Eqs. 1 and 2).

This is consistent with the behaviour of metal oxide nanoparticles reported in the literature [39,40]. Above pH = 9.0 and below pH = 3.0, it is evident that the particles became strongly anionic/cationic and can be considered highly stable (particles with value of $\zeta > \pm 30$ mV) [41].

Fig. 3B shows the hydrodynamic particle size and distribution of prepared samples measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS). The DLS results suggest that the ceria particles are well dispersed in water (measured at native pH). The mean particle size was found to be 2054, 1312, 1075, 1773, and 782 nm for the Ce-UREA, Ce-AMN, Ce-HMT, Ce-CARB, and Ce-PER samples, respectively. The DLS data are not fully consistent with SEM and XRD observations, which can be caused by the easier formation of bigger agglomerates in an aqueous solution. The samples that were calcined (Ce-UREA, Ce-CARB) exhibit a larger particle size, which is due to sintering and formation of bigger agglomerates. Conversely, samples that were only dried (Ce-AMN, Ce-PER, Ce-HMT) show a smaller size of particles/agglomerates.

The average particle size (diameter) and the polydispersity index (PDI) are presented in Table 3. The PDI index is below 0.30, providing evidence of uniform particle size distribution in addition to the good suspension stability of ceria samples in water at native pH [42]. This suggests that most particles are relatively similar in size, although some differences exist among the samples. The differences in pH(PZC) and pH(IEP), see Tables 2 and 3, can be connected with the fact that: a) The isoelectric point (IEP) values reflect the external surface charges of nanomaterials in solution, marking the pH at which the zeta potential of the surface or molecule $\zeta = 0$. The IEP value represents the pH at which ceria particles remain stationary in an electric field [43]; while b) the pH (PZC) corresponds to the total net surface charge distribution (internal and external) of ceria particles. It is defined as the negative logarithm of the activity of the ions that determine the potential, where the net surface charge distribution is balanced ($\sigma_{\text{OH}_2^+} = \sigma_{\text{OH}^-}$) and the surface concentrations are equal ($[\text{MO}^-] = [\text{MOH}_2^+]$) [44–46].

Typically, the pH(IEP) and pH(PZC) are the same if no other reactions or adsorption processes occur [45]. Differences between pH(IEP)

and pH(PZC) and the shift in pH(IEP) values, either lower or higher, are primarily caused by the specific adsorption of cations or anions from the electrolyte used during zeta potential measurement [47,48]. Acid-base titration, in contrast, is based on the transfer of OH^- and H_3O^+ ions between the ionizable surface groups of ceria, which is the fundamental involved reaction. Zeta potential (electrophoretic mobility), however, corresponds to the external surface charge potential. Corapcioglu et al. [49] noted that zeta potential measurements may provide misleading data, whereas acid-base titration offers more accurate quantitative insights into the surface acidity of nanomaterials. Variations between pH (PZC) and pH(IEP) indicate greater heterogeneity in prepared ceria sample and can be attributed to the specific adsorption of cations or anions from the background electrolyte, as well as differences in the nature, purity, hydrolysis, sample preparation history, aging, experimental protocols, or the crystallinity of the sample [47].

3.5. pH change during the dephosphorylation

The pH during the dephosphorylation reaction was first investigated (Fig. 4A) and the buffer capacity was calculated (Fig. 4B). The data were measured for both model compounds 1-NPPH and 2-NPPH, and similar results were obtained for both; therefore, only the data for 1-NPPH are shown. The data for the buffered reaction is listed in SI (see Fig. S3 B, C). From the titration curves, the approximate buffer capacity β of individual samples was calculated. The buffer capacity can be expressed using the following equation (Eq. 3):

$$\beta = \frac{\Delta B}{\Delta \text{pH}} \quad (3)$$

where, ΔB is the molar amount of the base added to the reaction mixture during the titration process, causing a pH change of ΔpH .

The individual buffer curves correspond to the ability of nanoceria to buffer pH in a given pH range. The buffer capacity of ceria samples is influenced by their intrinsic activity. The buffer capacity for individual samples decreases in the following order: Ce-HMT > Ce-UREA = Ce-CARB > Ce-PER = Ce-AMN. The data are well correlated to the ability of samples to keep the pH value constant during the reaction. If the pH significantly changed during the reaction, the maximum buffer capacity was low (Fig. 4B, Ce-PER and Ce-AMN); when the maximum buffer capacity is higher (Fig. 4B, Ce-HMT, Ce-CARB, and Ce-UREA), the pH remains stable during the dephosphorylation.

3.6. Dephosphorylation of 1/2-NPPH under different pH

Two similar compounds (1- or 2-NPPH) were used to evaluate the effect of substituent position on the dephosphorylation. The structure of

Fig. 5. Dephosphorylation reactions of 1-NPPH (A) and 2-NPPH (B) on ceria and creation of the main degradation products, i.e., 1-NP and 2-NP under ambient conditions (298 K).

Fig. 6. Comparison of pseudo-first-order rate constants for decomposition of 1-NPPH (A) and 2-NPPH (B) on prepared ceria samples under various pH at 298 K in the aqueous solutions.

Fig. 7. Comparison of pseudo-first-order rate constants for creation of 1-NP (A) and 2-NP (B) on prepared ceria samples under various pH at 298 K in the aqueous solutions.

1/2-NPPH and their main degradation products are shown in Fig. 5. The reaction was studied under three different pH (without pH adjustment, pH = 4.5 and pH = 8.2).

The measured data were fitted using mathematical models for the pseudo-first-order kinetics (Eqs. 4 and 5), and the kinetic parameters obtained by non-linear regression are listed in Tables S2 and S3.

$$c_t^{NPPH} = c_\infty^{NPPH} + c_0^{NPPH} \cdot e^{-k_1^{NPPH} \cdot t} \quad (4)$$

$$c_t^{NP} = c_1^{NP} \cdot (1 - e^{-k_1^{NP} \cdot t}) \quad (5)$$

In Eq. 4 is the c_t^{NPPH} the 1/2-NPPH concentration at time t (min), c_0^{NPPH} the fraction of 1/2-NPPH degraded during the experiment, and c_∞^{NPPH} the residual concentration of 1/2-NPPH at the end of the reaction (i.e., equilibrium), k_1^{NPPH} (min⁻¹) the pseudo-first-order rate constant, which may describe all processes contributing to the 1/2-NPPH disappearance (both adsorption and chemical destruction).

Fig. 8. Normalized kinetic curves for 1-NPPH degradation and 1-NP formation on prepared ceria samples under various pH, i.e., without pH adjustment (A), pH = 4.5 (B) and pH = 8.2 (C).

Fig. 9. Normalized kinetic curves for 2-NPPH degradation and 2-NP formation on prepared ceria samples under various pH, i.e., without pH adjustment (A), pH = 4.5 (B) and pH = 8.2 (C).

In Eq. 5 the c_t^{NP} and c_1^{NP} are the relative concentrations of 1/2-NP produced by the degradation of 1/2-NPPH at the time t (min) and in equilibrium or by a faster process, respectively. The k_1^{NP} (min^{-1}) corresponds to the pseudo-first-order rate constant for the 1/2-NP formation.

The pseudo-first-order fitted well on the measured data (considered R^2 in Tables S2 and S3), and the normalized kinetics curves are presented in Figs. 8 and 9. As evident, the balance is not equimolar, and probably part of 1/2-NP remains adsorbed on the ceria surface. To evaluate the 1/2-NP adsorption as the only formed product, the adsorption kinetics of 1/2-NP itself on all samples in deionized water without pH adjustment were measured (see Fig. S4 A, B). A comparison of the rate constants for 1/2-NPPH dephosphorylation and 1/2-NP creation is shown in Figs. 6 and 7. Ceria ability to decompose various organophosphates has already been demonstrated elsewhere [20,50,51]. 1/2-NPPH constitutional isomers were used to evaluate whether the position of the phosphoester bond on the same organic backbone affects the ability of different ceria to cleave the P—O—aryl bond, and these isomers are primarily used for studying enzyme kinetics and activity [4, 11,17]. According to the data summarized in Tables S2 and S3, the ceria synthesis procedure significantly affected the rate constants, 1/2-NPPH conversion rate, and degree of conversion of 1/2-NPPH into 1/2-NP.

As can be seen (Table S2, Fig. 6), the rate of 1-NPPH dephosphorylation in the water without pH adjustment decreases in the following order: Ce-PER > Ce-UREA > Ce-CARB > Ce-HMT > Ce-AMN, whereas for 2-NPPH decreases in that order: Ce-UREA > Ce-PER > Ce-AMN > Ce-CARB > Ce-HMT. The Ce-PER, as the sample with the largest surface area and the number of defects in the crystal lattice and oxygen-containing surface functional groups [27], shows the fastest 1-NPPH dephosphorylation due to the high availability of the active sites. On the other hand, Ce-UREA with planar particle morphology and mesoporous structure can provide good access to the active site for the P—O—aryl bond cleavage, as was shown previously [14]; also the materials with higher alkalinity facilitate the cleavage of the P—O—aryl bond. The relatively high rate constants for Ce-UREA (for both 1/2-NPPH) in the experiment without pH adjustment were thus attributed to the nature of Ce-UREA, primarily to its higher alkalinity.

In our previous work, we found that the number of surface hydroxyl groups is strongly related to the material's activity in phosphoester hydrolysis and there was an optimal value among the CeO₂ samples tested [52]. For instance, cerium oxides synthesized at lower calcination temperature typically retain a significant amount of —OH groups. However, their crystalline structure remains underdeveloped, preventing efficient reformation of active sites (i.e., Ce³⁺ generation through oxygen vacancy migration). Conversely, in cerium oxides produced at higher temperatures, the Ce³⁺ concentration is no longer the limiting factor, and the overall reaction rate is instead strongly influenced by the —OH groups concentration.

In general, cerium oxides synthesized at low to moderate temperatures have high concentrations of —OH groups, making the chemical reaction between PO and —OH groups no longer the rate-limiting step. We propose that the activity of cerium oxides prepared under these conditions may be rather influenced by their morphology or crystallinity [53].

Under acidic conditions (pH = 4.5), the rate constants for Ce-CARB, Ce-HMT, Ce-PER, and Ce-AMN (for 2-NPPH) increased significantly compared to the experiment without pH adjustment. The rate constants for P—O—aryl bond cleavage were notably highest at acidic pH for most samples, consistent with the findings of Kuchma et al. [3]. Interestingly, the rate constant for Ce-AMN increased approx. 4 times (2-NPPH) and 5 times (1-NPPH) in an acidic pH compared to pH = 8.2 and when pH was not adjusted. In the alkaline region, all samples showed comparable rate constants for both 1-NPPH and 2-NPPH, with exceptions observed for Ce-AMN and Ce-PER (1-NPPH). Similarly, Ce-CARB, Ce-HMT, and Ce-UREA exhibited comparable rate constants across the pH range, except for Ce-HMT in the case of 2-NPPH without pH adjustment.

Zhang et al. [10] studied the pH dependence of P—O—aryl bond-containing molecules on the reaction rate constant and reported a strong correlation between the reaction rate constant and pH. For the reaction to proceed in acid pH, the molecule must contain a group capable of ionization, which needs to be deprotonated for the reaction (i. e., dephosphorylation). In contrast, at alkaline pH, the reaction rate constant depends on the leaving group. Since the same leaving group is cleaved for both substrates (1/2-NPPH) in our case, the rate constant values at alkaline pH are also comparable. It can be thus assumed that at alkaline pH, the rate-determining step is the cleavage of the P—O—aryl bond.

Without pH adjustment, the rate-determining step will depend on the inherent acidity or basicity of the ceria sample. The effect of solution pH plays a role in the surface charge and affect the size of aggregates that also contribute to the activity of material [54]. Hence, one of the main parameters governing adsorption is the point of zero charge (PZC) of the surface, which can be slightly different for each sample. In an acidic medium, the surface is predominantly positively charged, and effectively attracts the organophosphate in its anionic form, thereby improving adsorption and subsequent reaction. [55]. 1/2-NPPH has a pKa₁ of 1.24 and pKa₂ of 5.38, meaning it is predominantly ionized above this pH, non-ionized below this value, and partly ionized in between. At pH above pKa, e.g. 6, 1/2-NPPH exists mainly in its anionic form, leading to repulsive interactions with the negatively charged surface of some ceria samples. In contrast, at pH between the pKa_{1,2}, 1/2-NPPH is partly ionized, favoring adsorption on the positively charged surface which can enhance the degradation.

Generally, higher rate constants were calculated for 2-NPPH than for 1-NPPH for all samples. This is likely related to the more favorable spatial orientation of the phosphate group on the benzene rings. The reaction of 2-NPPH is unlikely to be sterically blocked by the proximity of the aromatic rings, as it may be in the case of 1-NPPH [4]. The presence of additional substituents on the organic backbone can further affect the ability of nucleophilic agents to attack phosphoester bonds in the molecule and moderately influences sensitivity to steric hindrance [11,56]. Also, the hydrolysis of aryl phosphates is assisted by electron-attracting substituents and retarded by electron-donating substituents [5]. However, as no additional substituents are present in the investigated molecule, another mechanism must be involved. It was found that 1-NPPH is a much worse substrate than 2-NPPH for tyrosine-specific phosphatases, primarily due to steric hindrance [11]. Therefore, the differences in rate constants and reactivity are likely influenced by the steric hindrance of the aromatic rings and partially also by the different physicochemical properties of ceria samples (see our previous works [27,57]).

Furthermore, a preferred mechanism of dephosphorylation involves proton transfer to the phenolic oxygen atom and elimination of metaphosphate ion, i.e., hydrolysis of phenol is more likely than hydrolysis of phenoxide ion. The proton transfer is further reinforced by water molecules [5]. According to Butcher et al. [23], the primary product of phosphate ester hydrolysis is an alcohol and a monomeric metaphosphate ion (PO₃⁻). These monomeric metaphosphates have been identified as the main intermediates in phosphorylation processes. The subsequent breakdown of the intermediate occurs because the formation of alcohol is easier than the formation of the high-energy anion (RO⁻). As the pH increases, the phosphate ester is more likely to be present in the form of the dianion ROPO₃⁻, which does not readily react with hydroxide ions due to the electrostatic repulsion between the negative charges on the ions. This explains why the rate of dephosphorylation can be faster at pH 4.5 than at pH 8.2.

The Ce-HMT exhibits a low degree of conversion, which is most likely related to the smallest BET surface area, i.e., the active sites for decomposition are quickly saturated and probably occupied by the NPPH decomposition product, which block further reaction. When the phosphate group is more distant from the organic backbone, the potential effects and electrostatic interactions with the aromatic rings are

Fig. 10. FTIR spectra of pure 1-NP, Ce-CARB after adsorption of 1-NP and Ce-CARB (A), and pure 1-NPPH, Ce-CARB after reaction of 1-NPPH and Ce-CARB sample (B).

suppressed and limited. In the case of 1-NPPH, the adsorption of benzene rings on the ceria surface may preferentially occur, thereby blocking the active sites of ceria involved in the cleavage of the P—O—aryl bond [4,5,10].

According to Yao et al. [58], a higher reaction rate for dephosphorylation can be expected at higher pH values. Nevertheless, they used p-nitrophenyl phosphate as a model compound and a series of porous ceria nanorods, and thus the influence of other substituents on the organic backbone can be present [11,56]. Kuchma et al. [3] observed the positive effect of acidic pH (consistent with our investigation) on the dephosphorylation of p-nitrophenyl phosphate on ceria nanoparticles. The faster reaction in acidic pH may be due to a different reaction mechanism [25] or possible changes in surface charge at different pH values [33] and the number of Lewis acid/base active sites [59]. The high experimental error values in Figs. 6 and 7 are related to the significant heterogeneity of the samples and potential imperfections in ceria particles. Additionally, for samples exhibiting substantial experimental error, this can be attributed to differences in pore size and distribution, specifically for Ce-HMT (1-NPPH), Ce-UREA, and Ce-HMT (1-NP). The higher experimental error values for the formation of 1-NP (Ce-UREA and Ce-HMT) can be ascribed to variations in pore size and distribution, which may be linked to differences in the desorption rate and mechanism of the product from the ceria surface.

3.7. FTIR study of 1/2-NPPH interaction with ceria

The interaction of 1/2-NPPH and 1/2-NP with ceria samples was also studied by FTIR (Fig. 10 A, B). As similar results were obtained for all ceria samples, only the data for Ce-CARB are shown. In Fig. 10A, characteristic bands for 1-NP correspond to the in-plane vibrations $\delta(\text{OH})$, localized at 1279 and 1259 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(\text{C-H})$ stretching vibrations are localized between 3200 and 3000 cm⁻¹, with the band around 3055 cm⁻¹ ascribed to $\nu(\text{C-H})$ stretching modes. The in-plane bending vibrations $\delta(\text{C-H})$ are located at 1458 cm⁻¹ and between 1240 and 1140 cm⁻¹. The out-of-plane bending vibrations $\gamma(\text{C-H})$ can be found between 965 and 875 cm⁻¹ and at 787 and 765 cm⁻¹. The ring stretching modes of 1-NP (C—C, C=C) are localized in the region 1600–790 cm⁻¹, which agrees well with Muzomwe et al. [60]. Similar bands were found for NPPH, as evident from the spectra in Fig. 10B. Also in Fig. 10A and B, the FTIR spectra of the ceria samples with typical bands for CeO₂ [61] are presented.

Several characteristic bands appeared in the spectra after the NPPH dephosphorylation reaction and NP adsorption on ceria. The main changes are visible between 1200 and 900 cm⁻¹, where the new bands overlapped with the characteristic bands corresponding to carbonaceous species (O—C—O) on the ceria surface. The new bands in this region correspond to the ring stretching modes of 1-NP (Fig. 10A) and out-of-plane bending vibrations $\gamma(\text{C-H})$ [60,62]. The new peak localized in

the range of 1150–1000 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the asymmetric and ν_3 vibration of the P—O bond [63,64]. The new strong band at 1133 cm⁻¹ (Ce-CARB 1-NPPH, Fig. 10B) can be attributed to $-\text{PO}_4$ stretching vibrations [65]. The new bands (after 1-NP/1-NPPH adsorption/reaction) localized in the region of 1600–790 cm⁻¹ correspond to the ring in-plane and out-of-plane bending modes of the NP/NPPH aromatic ring [60,66]. This confirms that some residues of NP/NPPH remain after adsorption/reaction on the ceria surface, and the residual active sites could be blocked for further reactions.

4. Conclusions

A set of ceria samples prepared by several methods was studied for the decomposition of model organophosphorus compounds NPPH in water at different pH. It was observed that the rate of dephosphorylation was higher at acidic conditions but was different for each sample due to the different reaction mechanism involved and the nature of the ceria samples. Furthermore, the substituent position on the organic backbone significantly affects the decomposition of 1- or 2-NPPH. The naphthyl phosphate isomer with the substituent in position 2 (2-NPPH) exhibits faster decomposition on all ceria samples, likely due to reduced steric hindrance of the organic backbone. As confirmed by FTIR, NPPH and NP strongly interact with the ceria surface forming surface-bound residues. The lower rate constants for several samples may be attributed to the surface being blocked by NPPH or its resulting product, which adsorbs onto the surface and blocks further reaction of NPPH. The higher adsorption of NPPH on some ceria samples can be attributed to the close proximity of the pH(PZC) values to the pKa value of NPPH isomers. The results obtained here can provide valuable insights into the decomposition of structurally similar compounds on the surface of nanocrystalline oxides, which may be relevant for both biological [67–69] or environmental application [11,70,71] of the reactive nanooxides.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Henych Jirí: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization, Ederer Jakub: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Janoš Pavel:** Supervision, Conceptualization. **Kolská Zdenka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **Rysánek Petr:** Investigation, Data curation. **Neubertová Viktorie:** Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2025.116460](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2025.116460).

Data availability

The raw data required to reproduce the above findings are available to download from <https://zenodo.org/records/15075145>

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